

Chemical Investigation of the Leaves of *Xanthium strumarium* Linn

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Strumasterol (identical with poriferasterol, a C-24 epimer of stigmasterol) and oleic acid from the petroleum ether extract and 3,4-dihydroxy cinnamic acid, β -sitosterol-D-glucoside, a chalcone derivative have been isolated from the alcoholic extract of the leaves of *Xanthium strumarium* Linn. The leaves also contain KCl, carbohydrates and an unidentified hydroxy compound.

WE have reported¹ earlier the isolation of compound D, m. p. 156-157° from the leaves of *X. strumarium* and now identified as poriferasterol^{2,3} (a C-2H epimer of stigmasterol⁴, strumasterol IR, NMR, MS and preparation of acetate and benzoate). From the initial fraction of chromatography of the saponified part of petroleum ether (60-80°) extract an oily liquid was obtained and identified as oleic acid⁵.

During the course of the present investigations the alcoholic extract of the defatted leaves on cooling gave white needles (compound I) of high m. p. (>350°) which showed the presence of hydroxyl group (s) (IR) and KCl from the concentrated extract. After removal of the above components, the filtrate was evaporated to almost dryness and the residue divided into methanol soluble and insoluble parts. The chromatographic separation of the methanol soluble part furnished compounds II, III and IV. The compound II was characterised as 3, 4-dihydroxy cinnamic acid (m.m.p., UV, IR, co-paper chromatography and preparation of diacetate and methyl ester). The compound III, C₂₇H₄₆O₆, m. p. 290-292° was revealed to be β -sitosterol-D-glucoside by its colour reactions, m. m. p., co-TLC, acid hydrolysis (β -sitosterol and D-glucose) and preparation of its tetraacetate, m.p. 169-170°. The compound IV, C₁₆H₁₄O₄, m.p. 170-171°, appeared to be a chalcone derivative by its colour reactions and spectral analysis (UV & IR), being under study will be reported later. The paper chromatography of the methanol insoluble part revealed the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose.

Experimental

Petroleum ether extract: The compound D was isolated as described¹ earlier from the nonsaponifiable part of the petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the leaves of this plant and the saponified part after working up in the usual manner, and chromatography yielded an yellow oily liquid in the initial fraction which was charcoaled to give colourless liquid (oleic acid).

Strumasterol (compound D): The compound D was crystallised from C₆H₆ : MeOH (1:1) as colourless needles (330 mg), m.p. 156-157°; (Found: C, 84.27; H, 11.55%; calcd. for C₂₉H₄₈O: C, 84.46; H, 11.63%); ν_{max} . (Nujol) 3400-3250, 3025, 1655, 1630, 1060, 1050, 1020, 980, 972, 958, 837, 800 cm⁻¹ etc.; NMR(CDCl₃) τ 9.31 (s, CH₃ at C-10), 9.00 (s, CH₃ at C-13), 9.05~8.93 (d, CH₃ at C-20), 9.22~9.15 (d, two CH₃ at C-25), 9.25~9.15~9.07 (t, CH₃ at C-28), 8.84-7.82 (c, protons of CH₂ & CH groups of the cyclic system and side chain), 7.68 (s, OH), 6.50 (m, br, H of C-3), 4.88 (q, 2H at C-22 & C-23), 4.65 (d, br, H of C-6); MS m/e 412 (M⁺), 397, 394, 379, 273, 255, 231, 213 etc. It was identical with poriferasterol. The identity was further confirmed by preparation of its acetate, m.p. 143-144° and benzoate, m.p. 140-141°.

Oleic acid: The colourless liquid (3.9 ml), b. p. 285° at 100 mm, solidifying point 13°, was identified as oleic acid by preparation⁷ of its dibromide, solidifying point 28°; 9,10-dihydroxy stearic acid, m.p. 129-130° and amide, m.p. 75-76°.

Alcoholic extract: The defatted powdered leaves (2 kg) were extracted exhaustively in Soxhlet with 95% alcohol. The alcoholic extract on cooling gave white needles (compound I) which were separated and the filtrate after concentration and keeping in a refrigerator for 48 hrs. yielded KCl. Further, the concentrated solution was reduced to almost dryness and divided into methanol soluble and insoluble parts. The methanol soluble part was chromatographed over silica gel (250 g) with ethyl acetate and methanol mixture in different proportions yielding compounds II, III and IV.

Compound I: It was crystallised from H₂O as white crystals (390 mg), melted at >350°, charred, again became white and finally sublimed; (Found: C, 41.14; H, 6.78%; Emp. formula CH₂O); ν_{max} . (KBr) 3475, 3410, 3306, 2910, 2875, 2070, 1630, 1378, 1345, 1208, 1116, 1099, 980, 620 cm⁻¹. The acetate (Ac₂O/H₂SO₄

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method) of the compound changed colour from white to yellow at 200° and decomposed before melting at 270-272°. It, however, could not be identified due to lack of evidence.

3,4-Dihydroxy cinnamic acid (compound II): From EtOAc: MeOH (2:1) fraction, yellow needles (710 mg), m.p. 196-197° (EtOAc: EtOH, 4:1); (Found: C, 59.48; H, 5.11%; calcd. for $C_9H_9O_4$: C, 59.67; H, 4.97%); λ_{max}^{EtOH} 226, 290, 330 nm; ν_{max} (Nujol) 3450-3400, 3300-3220, 2700-2550, 1670, 1620, 1600, 1575, 1500, 1450, 1265, 1255, 975 cm^{-1} etc.; diacetate, m.p. 189-190° and methyl ester, m.p. 151-152°. The above analysis, m.m.p. and co-paper chromatography confirmed it to be 3,4-dihydroxy cinnamic acid.

β -Sitosterol-D-glucoside (compound III): From EtOAc: MeOH (1:2) fraction, colourless plates (660mg), m.p. 290-292° (Pyr.-MeOH mixture) (Found: C, 73.01; H, 10.68%; calcd. for $C_{35}H_{50}O_6$: C, 72.92; H, 10.42%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3450-3400, 2950, 2840, 1650, 1475, 1380, 1360, 1060, 1100-800 cm^{-1} (sugar moiety). It gave positive tests for sterol, carbohydrate and unsaturation and on acid hydrolysis (7% H_2SO_4), β -sitosterol, m.p. 136-137° (colour reaction, m.m.p., co-TLC, IR and acetate 128°) and D-glucose (paper chromatography). These analysis revealed it to be β -sitosterol-D-glucoside and was further confirmed by m.m.p., co-TLC and preparation of tetraacetate, m.p. 169-170°.

A chalcone derivative (compound IV): From EtOAc: MeOH (1:5) fraction, yellow needles (480 mg), m.p. 170-171° (EtOH); (Found: C, 71.24; H, 5.04%; calcd. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$: C, 71.11; H, 5.19%); λ_{max}^{MeOH} 244, 305 (infl.), 370 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3300-3250 (OH), 2910, 2820 (CH & OCH_3), 1640 (C=O), 1625 (C=C), 1610, 1575, 1515, 1440 (C-C), 1265 (C- OCH_3), 1205 cm^{-1} (C-OH) etc.. It gave bright yellow colour with

alkali producing yellow colour with alc. $FeCl_3$ and was soluble in alkali producing yellow colour solution but did not respond to Shinoda test (Mg-HCl).

The methonal insoluble part gave positive Molisch test for carbohydrates. The ascending paper chromatography on Whatman paper No. 1 using n-BuOH: AcOH: H_2O (4:1:5, V/V) as solvent system and aniline hydrogen phthalate as spray reagent revealed the presence of glucose, fructose and sucrose which were further confirmed by co-paper chromatography with pure specimens.

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